

MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A READING CULTURE

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Abstract: This article is dedicated to the significance of modern approaches in shaping the reading culture and their role in promoting reading among young people. The reading culture plays an essential role in the intellectual and spiritual development of society. The impact of modern technologies, internet platforms, the development of libraries and educational centers, targeted reading methods, and digital reading platforms are discussed. The article highlights the importance of these contemporary approaches in creating new opportunities for young people and shaping a modern reading culture.

Keywords: reading culture, modern approaches, internet platforms, digital books, libraries, educational centers, targeted reading, youth, reading habits, technology, interactive reading, books, activities.

Reading culture is an activity that focuses on reading books, education and enlightenment, which plays an important role in the spiritual and intellectual development of young people and society. In modern society, the need to implement new and effective approaches to the formation of a reading culture is always of great importance. Therefore, it is very important to study the importance of reading books, modern methods and approaches aimed at it.

Using the Internet and digital information sources: Today, the Internet and digital platforms and resources create new opportunities for the formation of a reading culture. Electronic books (e-books), audiobooks, podcasts and online courses increase the interest of young people in reading. These technologies not only make it easy to find books, but also make them read anywhere and at any time. Reading

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is not limited to books, but also includes videos, articles and even interactive materials.

Creating a spiritual and intellectual environment: The culture of reading depends on the spiritual environment in society. Modern approaches, especially in promoting reading, are aimed at creating a special environment for different segments of the population. For example, book clubs, projects held in libraries, activities on books and their discussion on social networks increase interest in reading among young people. In addition, they help to exchange news, ideas and experiences.

The impact of technological advances: For most modern young people, technology and digital innovations are new ways of reading books. For example, interactive books, that is, books enriched with multimedia elements, videos and graphics, make the reading process as interesting and enjoyable as necessary. Such books introduce the reader to new methods and encourage them to create a modern "reading" for themselves.

Purposeful and clearly focused reading: In modern approaches, the organization of purposeful reading systems for young people is important in forming a reading culture. Focused reading directions in accordance with the interests of young people in choosing books and sources will give them effective results. This approach ensures the formation of excellent knowledge and helps people search for the information they need.

Development of libraries and educational centers: Modern libraries are not only a place to store books, but also become an important center for communication, knowledge exchange and assistance for students. Seminars, lectures, book presentations organized in libraries and trainings held in educational centers are part of modern approaches aimed at forming a reading culture of young people, where opportunities for spiritual and intellectual enrichment are created for each person.

Development of digital reading platforms: In recent years, the development of digital platforms in the reading habits of young people has increased significantly. These platforms provide opportunities for reading and discussing books, as well as getting acquainted with modern books and writers. In addition, the opportunity to directly communicate with authors and discuss books on some platforms also increases the interest of young people.

The social and secret function of the book: The modern approach to reading should not forget that the book has a social role. Books, in particular, bring confidence, inspiration and news to the reader. Discussions with young people, educators and other people in the social environment are of great importance in this regard. Therefore, reading books is not limited to personal development, but also contributes to social and cultural transformation.

Modern approaches play an important role in forming a reading culture. Many innovative methods, digital technologies, the development of libraries and educational centers increase interest in reading. For modern youth, reading books becomes an important factor not only in personal development, but also in improving social and cultural skills.

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